

FOCCUS

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D10.3 Inventory of EU coastal operational systems

WP10: Dissemination, communication, and uptake

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Glossary and Abbreviations

+ATLANTIC	+ATLANTIC CoLAB
ADRIFS	Adriatic Forecasting System
BGC	Biogeochemistry (used as a category of Copernicus Marine Service product only)
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center of Climate Change
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CWG	Coastal Working Group
DCSM-FM	Delft3D Coastal Systems Model - Flexible Mesh
DELTAES	Stichting Deltaes
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
HEREON	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon
ICE	Sea Ice (used as a category of Copernicus Marine Service product only)
LFCS	Lazio Coast Forecasting System
MET.NO	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
ML	Machine Learning
MOi	Mercator Ocean International
MS	Member States
OBS	Observations
OOFS	Operational Ocean Forecasting System
OP-DCC	OceanPrediction Decade Collaborative Centre
PHY	Physics (used as a category of Copernicus Marine Service product only)
RBINS	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
SHOM	Service Hydrographique et Océanographique de la Marine
SOCIB	Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System
SPM	Suspended Particulate Matter
TAC	Thematic Assembly Centre
WAV	Waves (used as a category of Copernicus Marine Service product only)
WMOP	Western Mediterranean Operational Model
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

FOCCUS Task 10.2.1 aims to inventory existing operational ocean forecasting systems (Oofs) managed by EU Member States, focusing on their maturity, application scope, and reliance on external data. The task also identifies specific needs and expectations these systems have from Copernicus Marine Service regional products. The results will support Mercator Ocean International in developing a strategy to enhance the interface between regional and coastal systems.

We started by reviewing past inventory initiatives considered to be relevant to the present exercise, detailing their context and summarising the information they bring with respect to the specific objectives outlined above. This includes:

- The EuroGOOS Coastal Working Group inventory,
- The Copernicus Marine Service Member State Forum,
- The OceanPrediction Decade Collaborative Centre (OP-DCC) Atlas,
- Census achieved in the frame of FOCCUS WP6.

From this basis, it appeared necessary to narrow the description of the composition and activity of the European Oofs community, to detail current practices in terms of Copernicus Marine Service products usage, and to establish a link between recommendations and thematic sector of activity (hydrodynamics, waves, biogeochemistry and sea ice). Originally planned to be completed at the end of 2024, this deliverable was granted a six month extension in order to better exploit the synergy between networking and conference events which occurred in the end of 2024 and beginning of 2025, and to lower the burden on contributors and enhance our chances of collecting contributions by enlarging the timeframe over which the survey was open to contribution. The survey was designed and distributed through the FOCCUS, EuroGOOS, OceanPrediction and Member State Forum channels, collecting contributions from January to May 2025.

Analysis of the collected answers (from 34 European Oofs) reveals a strong and growing usage of Copernicus Marine Service products, with high user willingness to further engage. Among those currently using non-Copernicus Marine Service products, approximately 70% are open to transitioning to Copernicus Marine Service products within the next three years, 20% cite product quality limitations and 10% find technical challenges too demanding. These figures reflect both a high level of trust in Copernicus Marine Service and a clear expectation for continued product development.

The survey confirms previous inventories in highlighting a notable disparity in the operational status of Oofs across different thematics. Biogeochemical systems are underrepresented, comprising only 6–18% depending on the source. It seems that many biogeochemical models exist for specific applications but lack full operational deployment. Barriers include data availability, technical processing burdens, and institutional constraints. Targeted actions—such as easing data workflows or supporting operationalization efforts—could help unlock these systems. The OP-DCC Atlas could play a strategic role in unlocking the operationalization of these systems, potentially linking support services

tailored to specific user categories. To support broader uptake, its scope should be extended to include quasi-operational systems, sorted by readiness levels.

The FOCCUS and OceanPrediction Atlas survey results underscore the interconnected nature of the OOFS landscape: 66% of systems both receive and provide boundary conditions from other OOFS, and many span multiple thematics. Strengthening Europe's OOFS capacity, thus, requires an interoperable data exchange framework across all systems, not just from centralized Copernicus Marine Service components to locally operated systems. Improvements can trigger cascading benefits along spatial and thematic chains.

Adopting external forcings and implementing boundary conditions remain technical challenges. While some preprocessing steps (e.g., bias correction, downscaling) are common, many users report unique protocols, reflecting diverse modeling tools and concepts. Therefore, Copernicus Marine Service should aim not to provide one-size-fits-all products, but comprehensive datasets adaptable to varied needs—particularly in complex domains like sea ice and biogeochemistry. These products should be complemented by support tools, standards, and training. Though suggestions for centralized resources (e.g., workshops, GitHub repositories) received mixed feedback, some users support this idea.

Recommendations by thematic:

- **Physics:** Request for re-forecast models, long-term 3D hourly fields, and ensemble products. Observational needs include better quality control (possibly ML-based), faster near-real-time data delivery, and improved coastal/transitional coverage—particularly for tide gauges, buoys, and HF radar.
- **Waves:** Strong demand for a delivery of spectral information in both models and observations. Quality control and technical documentation (e.g., wave buoy specs) need enhancement.
- **Biogeochemistry:** Product's usability should reflect the thematic complexity (e.g., interpreting chlorophyll appropriately). Observational needs include better coastal coverage and expanded Bio-Argo float deployment. Interoperability between model, in-situ, and satellite data remains a challenge.
- **Sea-ice:** There is a clear recommendation to provide ice thickness in terms of classes, both for model and observation products. Attention should be given to the difference in class definitions between Ice TAC and regional models. Sea ice observation products near the coast are also missing.

2. Introduction and objectives

FOCCUS task 10.2.1 has for its lead objective to dress an inventory of existing, operational, coastal modelling systems operated by MS, in order to document their level of maturity, scope of applications and dependencies w.r.t external data (observations and forcings), and more specifically, to document their specific requirements and expectation from the regional products provided by the Copernicus Marine Service. This documentation effort should be tailored to support Mercator Ocean International (MOi), entrusted entity by the European Commission for the implementation of Copernicus Marine, in establishing a strategy towards improving the interface between regional systems, operated by Copernicus Marine Service forecasting centres and the coastal systems, operated by MS. Before FOCCUS, this interface was mostly conceived to provide one-way downstream information and data flow, from regional to coastal systems, but relevant specifications of upstream communication will be considered when available.

3. Previous and ongoing inventory efforts

3.1. The EuroGOOS Coastal Working Group inventory

3.1.1. Context

The Coastal Working Group is an organ of EuroGOOS, among other working groups, dedicated to promote the development of operational oceanography in coastal areas. Following its foundation in 2018, an overview analysis of the European capacity in terms of operational modeling of marine and coastal systems has been compiled and presented (Capet et al., 2020). This overview has been compiled from a survey conducted in 2018–2019 among members of EuroGOOS and its related network of Regional Operational Oceanographic Systems, addressing the purposes, context and technical specificities of operational modeling systems. Contributions to the survey were received from 49 organizations around Europe, which represent 104 operational model systems simulating mostly hydrodynamics, biogeochemistry and sea waves. The subsequent analyses highlighted the strengths and weaknesses of the coastal modelling capacity from an operational point of view, and led to the formulation of recommendations toward the improvement of marine operational modeling services in Europe.

3.1.2. Main conclusions

The study highlighted the heterogeneity of the European operational modeling capacity in terms of atmospheric and land boundary conditions, its limited deployment for biogeochemical phenomena, and a restricted use of data assimilation methods. In order to improve the accuracy of their simulations, model operators called for a further refinement of spatial resolution, and identified the **quality and accessibility of forcing data** and the suitability of **observations for data assimilation** as restricting factors. The described issues call for **institutional integration efforts** and promotion of good practices to homogenize operational marine model implementations, and to ensure that external forcing datasets, observation networks and process formulations and parameterizations are adequately

developed to enable the deployment of high-level operational marine and coastal modeling services across Europe.

3.2. FOCCUS coastal systems

3.2.1. Context

In the context of project FOCCUS WP6 (Implementation of new interfaces and methodologies in coastal systems), roadmaps towards enhanced interfacing with Copernicus Marine Service were sketched by the different local models operated by members of the FOCCUS consortium as part of milestone MS6.1 (see Annex B). While addressing a restricted corpus (i.e., FOCCUS members only), these roadmaps target very specifically the issue of Copernicus Marine Service interfacing. Considered OOFs having fulfilled the roadmap are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: FOCCUS member's OOFs considered in FOCCUS WP6.

Partner	Area of Interest	Member States	Name of Member State Coastal System ¹	Interfaced with Copernicus Marine Service
MET.NO	Mainland Norway	Norway	Norkyst	ARC, BAL
HEREON	German Coastal Waters	Germany	GCoast-GB	NWS
HEREON	Western Black Sea	Germany, Romania	GCoast-BS	BS
DMI	Inner Danish Waters / Wadden Sea	Denmark, Germany	DKSS	NWS, BAL
Deltares	North Sea / Dutch Continental Shelf	Netherlands	DCSM-FM	GLOBAL
SHOM	Northwest France & Bay of Biscay	France	Tolosa	GLOBAL, IBI
SHOM	Northwest France & Bay of Biscay	France	CROCO	GLORYS12V1 IBI (in the future?)
CMCC	Adriatic Sea (Mediterranean)	Italy	AdriFS	MED
CMCC	Tyrrhenian Sea (Mediterranean)	Italy	LCFS	MED
SOCIB	Western Mediterranean - Balearic Sea	Spain	WMOP	MED
+ATLANTIC	Lisbon Metropolitan Area (Tagus / Sado estuaries)	Portugal	MOHID-LisOcean	GLOBAL

¹ cf. Table 1.2b in project description, see Annex B

3.2.2. Content

Each contributing OOFS was asked first to describe specific methodological items of their interfacing workflow with Copernicus Marine Service regional products, in order to help to identify common procedures. In a second step, contributing OOFS were asked to identify bottlenecks and main requirements. Finally, this effort led to the establishment of strategic roadmaps, as part of WP6 achievements. The answers are given below per OOFS, and then compiled and summarized at the end of the section.

Applied methodology

The information below originates from Roadmaps gathered in the context of FOCCUS milestone MS6.1 *“Interface Roadmaps for Improved Interfacing with Copernicus Marine Service”*, as described in D6.1 (see Annex B)².

WMOP

- **Chapman and Flather conditions** are used for sea level and barotropic velocities.
- **Mixed active-passive conditions** are used for temperature and salinity fields.
- A particular treatment including the alignment of model bathymetries and a **correction of interpolated velocities is applied at the Strait of Gibraltar** to ensure that the boundary forcing field properly represents the original inflow and outflow transports of the large-scale Copernicus Marine model.

LCFS & AdriFS

- The modelling approach is based on the downscaling of Copernicus Marine Service Marine products released at the regional scale of the Mediterranean Sea. The circulation core is **three-dimensionally downscaled** from Copernicus Marine Service-MED_PHY both in terms of initialization and open boundaries.
- **Clamped type open boundary conditions** were employed at the boundary for sea level and inflow active tracers.
- **Daily mean total velocities were nudged** at the open boundaries.
- **Zero gradient boundary conditions** were used for outflow active tracers.
- The sea level at the boundary is imposed by Copernicus Marine Service-MED_PHY **which includes the tidal signal**.
- The **wave core is downscaled** from Copernicus Marine Service-MED_WAV in terms of the open boundary. The parent model provides the child model with scalar wave fields, which are **used to generate the spectral wave action based on the Yamaguchi 1984** approach.

Croco-MANGA

- Eddy-resolving (1/12) global reanalysis (GLORYS12) is used to construct initial and open boundary conditions. The open boundary conditions are prescribed thanks to a characteristic based on **Rieman invariant method for the barotropic mode** (ssh and barotropic velocity components)

²

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1zdGhKniramRE9e4QHxpH9V6ZHZBxvU5ooTTaeyF974o/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.a0gy6070qgqi>

- The hydrological fields and baroclinic velocity components along the open boundaries are **processed according to a radiative algorithm**.
- The barotropic components of the flow (used in the characteristics algorithm) are computed by **linearly adding a tidal finite element solution (FES2014) to the barotropic flow component of GLORYS12**.
- The Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS) provides river discharge at a selected number of river outflows.
- Copernicus products are interfaced to our coastal model with [python packages under development](#)³

DCSM-FM

- Copernicus (blue and green) products are used as open boundary conditions to run regional domains at specific areas as one-way nested solutions. The domains are built with flexible mesh, which allows the representation of finer scale processes at the coast. We have automatic nesting procedures openly available in the [dfm tools](#)⁴.
- Satellite based SPM forcing based on a yearly average of MERIS (offshore) and yearly average Copernicus Marine Service SPM 100m (Wadden Sea) then a **cosine function applied with weekly timesteps**.

DKSS

- Current DKSS system uses dynamic two-way nesting to resolve estuarial-coastal-open sea interaction. The nesting system resolves both vertical and horizontal nesting, thus one executable resolves 7 subdomain setups, ranging from 0.1 n.m. to 3 n.m. The dynamic two-way system has been operated over two decades, and proved to be robust and high performance, which is especially suited for estuary-coastal forecasting. However, there are still a few weaknesses of the current system:
 - No data assimilation has been included in the operation although HBM model has been used to generate reanalysis with assimilation.
 - The North Sea boundary condition still uses T/S climatology, which can be improved by using Copernicus Marine Service data.
 - The river-sea interface: river discharges are currently treated as a source point. In a high resolution case, this will generate a few problems for big rivers: one is that the river water will pile up at the source point and generate abnormally high sea level; the other is that the scale of the estuary is not suitable for high resolution setup.

GCOAST

- Copernicus products are used as boundary conditions to run regional domains at specific areas as a one-way nest. The domains can be built with regular grids or unstructured models which allows the representation of fine details at coast.

Norkyst

- Currently Norkyst is only run operationally with physics, and uses a **combination of radiation and nudging conditions**, i.e. essentially the same procedures as proposed in Marchesiello *et al.* (2009).

³ https://crococean.gitlabpages.inria.fr/croco_pytools/index.html

⁴ https://github.com/Deltares/dfm_tools

- We also use tracer nudging in a relaxation zone, as well as having inflated horizontal diffusivities here, too. The main challenges today remain a **mismatch in hydrography (biases)** and **lack of detail in the currents in specific places** (e.g. the Atlantic water inflows).

Reported priorities of the roadmaps

WMOP

- We plan to **assimilate new coastal observations in the nested model**, from gliders, HF radar and high-resolution altimetry in particular.
- No change is planned in the implementation of the open boundary conditions.

LCFS & AdriFS

- We plan to advance with **a higher frequency of data at the boundary from Copernicus Marine Service-MED_PHY** (e.g., hourly values of velocity to be consistent with sea level).
- We plan to **calibrate the nudging procedures for velocity both temporally and spatially** to ensure a smoother transition from the parent model to the child model, thereby improving the overall stability and consistency of the nested models.
- We will explore the possibility of **developing a boundary condition for the barotropic component**.
- Additionally, we propose to **enhance the nesting process by incorporating AI-assisted methods**. This approach aims to increase the accuracy and efficiency of the wave action reconstruction process.

Croco-MANGA

- Consider using the Copernicus IBI-MFC product for initial and boundary conditions.
- Evaluate the improvement due to nudging on the equilibrated component of the flow through **a nudging term introduced in the density field evolution equations**. The nudging increment will also be computed from IBI-MFC.

DCSM-FM

- Improving consistency in physics between Copernicus Marine Service NEMO and 3D DCSM-FM on thermobaricity: **taking pressure into account in the Equation of State**. This will result in improved stability in the oceanic areas of 3D DCSM-FM, leading to better separation of water masses.
 - In Delft3D FM the EOS-80 Equation of State is applied, with the additional assumption of zero pressure. This implies that the stabilising effect thermobaricity (i.e., the increase of thermal expansion coefficient with increasing pressure) is ignored. The lack of pressure dependency is not valid in deep water (oceans and deep lakes). Stable stratification (in reality, or ocean model) can become unstable in Delft3D FM. The proposed improvement will fix this.
 - We will investigate computational efficiency as an increase in computational time should be minimised.
 - We will port the improvement to the General Availability release of the software, making it available to the coastal modelling community.

- We would like to test **better parameter mapping of BGC variables between Copernicus Marine Service and Delft3D-FM WAQ**
 - Testing what happens if organic nutrients and organic carbon is added to Copernicus Marine Service outputs, which would allow us to make less assumptions in our state variables (OPAL, POC, PON, POP). We assume that these state variables are calculated in Copernicus Marine Service models but not disseminated. This interface improvement exercise depends on the response from Copernicus Marine Service global BGC solution development team.
 - Similarly, we would like to test the impact of having Suspended sediment or KD (light attenuation) from Copernicus Marine Service models. According to our knowledge, this is not simulated currently, and it is not planned for the next release.
 - Note : this initiative will finally not be considered in the context of FOCCUS, as too few partners were concerned to justify asking for a Copernicus Marine Service release of such extended products. The point is discussed in Section 3 of D6.1
- In the DCSM-FM model we have the option of incorporating SPM simulations, but this requires additional computational time and validation. **Another option that we also use is to force the SPM field from Copernicus Marine Service satellite products and calculate only light attenuation that impacts water quality.** This satellite-based SPM forcing is currently rather simplistic, and we plan to improve it. As described above, satellite-based SPM forcing is currently based on a yearly average of MERIS product [offshore] and yearly average Sentinel-2 based Copernicus Marine Service SPM 100m satellite product [Wadden Sea] then a cosine function applied with weekly timesteps.
 - Our proposed improvement is to switch to higher resolution SPM satellite products offshore and apply daily time steps and use actual variation instead of applying a simplistic cosine variation.
- We will also update our in-house pre-/post-processing [tools](#), that also handle automatic nesting under Copernicus Marine Service ocean models, to follow the evolution of the Marine Data Store.

DKSS

- In FOCCUS project, we will develop effective ways of using Copernicus Marine Service model products to improve current DKSS system. This includes
 - using Copernicus Marine Service NWS-MFC model products to improve boundary conditions of surge and T/S in the North Sea boundaries;
 - using Copernicus Marine Service BAL-MFC and NWS-MFC analysis/reanalysis data to improve initial conditions of DKSS in the Baltic-North Sea
 - Aggregating Copernicus Marine Service forecasts in the Baltic-North Sea with DKSS forecasts, to improve DKSS forecast
- In addition, improved river forecasts from WP4/5 will be tested in DKSS.

GCOAST

- In addition to traditional boundary forcing, use of **nudging method within a sponge layer** allows harmonisation of the internal simulations with large scale physical or biogeochemical fields on subtidal scales.

Norkyst

- In parallel activities to FOCCUS, we want to **investigate bias correction schemes** based on archived in situ data.
- In addition, ROMS has support for two-way nesting, and some of the code can be adapted to **overcome the challenges associated with combined nudging/radiation conditions**. In FOCCUS we aim to explore these techniques to see if we can have less numerical artifacts along the boundaries.

3.2.3. Main conclusions

The items listed above provide valuable insights on interfacing challenges encountered by various teams, and envisioned solutions. These can be summarised as follows regarding the different thematic of ocean forecasting (it should be noted that none of the respondents specifically addressed the sea-ice thematic).

Hydrodynamics

For barotropic variables (sea level height and barotropic velocities) issues related to the adoption of clamped type boundary conditions may be overcome by applying more dynamic numerical schemes.

- Radiation and Orlandi conditions allow outgoing wave propagation and avoid artificial reflection of outgoing waves into the domain.
- Flather conditions allows balancing sea level and current interactions, and may enhance dynamic consistency
- Flow Relaxation Schemes (or nudging/relaxation) to reduce discontinuity and ensure smooth transitions at boundaries.

A right balance must be found between these approaches, and the need for specific calibration is often reported (e.g. diffusivity gradient and extent of the nudging boundary “sponge-layer”). One suggested that AI-assisted development may help solve these issues. It is not clear from the respondents how Copernicus Marine Service data provision may contribute to ease these developments or their application. Likely, it appears that Copernicus Marine Service support could take the form of proposing unified typology of boundary conditions, and providing support, guidelines and best practices for implementing and testing such approaches.

Several systems reported the need to correct prescribed boundary inflows (obtained from regional Copernicus Marine Service systems) based on bathymetric alignments between regional and local systems. Some consider the adoption of a bias correction scheme in that regard.

The need to align components of the density equation used respectively in the regional and local forecasting systems is mentioned twice, and/or to include such components in the information exchange at the boundary.

Depending on the upstream regional system of reference, the lack of high frequency resolution may constitute an issue that is handled in various ways. Finally, several OOFs consider switching from global to regional system upstream dependencies.

Biogeochemistry

A single system specifically addresses BGC thematics but does so in detail and likely raises points that are relevant for other systems.

One specific point of attention concerns the remapping between state variables of the regional and local modelling frameworks. The subset of variables disseminated by Copernicus Marine Service systems is reduced, probably to provide homogeneous datasets Europe-wide. This induces a necessity to re-map BGC variables (for instance from Copernicus Marine Service-prescribed chlorophyll to different groups of phytoplankton biomasses, or for different levels of details for stoichiometric composition). It is suggested that accessing all available variables produced in the regional systems might help in that regard (cf. FOCCUS D6.1, Sect 3.)

Another point concerns mismatches in the optical components ruling light extinction. The question lies in whether a full resolution for all components (e.g. SPM) should be considered locally, and constrained by corresponding boundary information, or whether the resulting light extinction parameters should be used instead.

3.3. Copernicus Marine Service Member State Forum

3.3.1. Context

In 2022, MOI set up the National Marine Stakeholder Forum (Marine Forum, <https://marine.copernicus.eu/about/national-marine-stakeholder-forum>) as a consultative assembly to foster interactions with Member States and contributing States. The ambition of the Marine Forum is also to facilitate the work of national delegates in the Copernicus User Forum and other governance bodies. The Marine Forum aims to support MOI in the implementation of the Copernicus programme within the marine domain, by promoting implications, synergies, and exchanges with MS. Strengthening the collaboration with MS and national entities in the marine domain, generating specific discussions for the Copernicus Marine Service, and integrating Copernicus Marine Service with MS expectations and assets the Marine Forum should help MOI in the preparation of its service and product portfolios to better respond to MS needs. The nomination of national representatives in the Marine Forum are at the discretion of the MS.

Starting from January 2023, a specific survey was conducted in the Marine Forum to collect a first overview of national coastal modelling activities and to identify their current link with the Copernicus Marine Service. Out of 21 members, 15 country representatives answered the survey (Germany, Sweden, Norway, France, Netherlands, Portugal, Belgium, Estonia,

Poland, Finland, United Kingdom, Spain, Ireland, Bulgaria, Greece). Specific interviews were conducted to complete the information collected from the structured survey form where needed.

The survey included questions relative to:

- Thematic of interests, and relationships with regional conventions and European policies and directives.
- Downstream dependencies in regard to Copernicus Marine Service products and services, and specific requirements.
- General needs in terms of enhancing coastal modelling capacity.

3.3.2. Main conclusions

- All respondent countries (15 out of 21 members) dispose of at least one fully operational modelling system, with a strong majority concerning hydrodynamic modelling, and a few countries with operational wave and biogeochemical modelling systems.
- All but a couple of national coastal modelling systems use Copernicus Marine products as boundary conditions. This should be complemented with information from the non-respondent countries.
- There is a common need to expand the coastal modelling systems with biogeochemistry and wave modelling capacity. The target resolution is 100 m for physical modelling and at least 500 m for biogeochemistry.
- An emerging need is to have more observation data and advanced tools to explore, analyse and synthesize ocean information.
- All countries are concerned and involved in the implementation of European Directives and Policies and, depending on their geographical context, countries are linked to at least one Regional Sea Convention.
- In terms of needs for the implementation of European Directives and Policies, the survey highlights a need for tools enabling the computation of derived quantities and to facilitate the handling and intercomparison of data.
- Interviewed members expressed interest in the inventory of coastal modelling systems provided here by FOCCUS.

A major drawback of this assessment lies in the fact that a single integrated response was provided per MS, instead of specific answers for each institution and/or specific to each implementation. Indeed, representatives may have not the full overview of the modelling activities and have expressed that other players should be solicited.

3.4. OceanPrediction Decade Collaborative Center - Atlas

3.4.1. Context

OceanPrediction Decade Collaborative Center (OP-DCC) is a cross-cutting structure of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, with the goal of promoting collaboration towards "a predicted ocean". The OceanPrediction community is currently compiling an [OceanPrediction Atlas](#) (link can be visited at the following URL:

<https://www.unoceanprediction.org/en/atlas/people/>) where the global forecasting community members, organisations, forecasting systems and services can be reported and queried. This atlas constitutes a major achievement towards the constitution of a global marine forecasting community, and by collecting technical information about OOFs’s production and dissemination procedures, paves the way towards a global digital twin of the ocean.

3.4.2. Content

The DCC atlas censuses 209 OOFs worldwide, 127 of which deliver products around European Seas. Reported European OOFs are maintained by a total of 42 institutions, which can now be reached through the Atlas’s database.

Figure 1 : (Left) Overview of forecasting systems reported in the global [OP-DCC Atlas](https://www.unoceanprediction.org/en/atlas/people/). (Right) Distribution per region.

While an in-depth analysis of the Atlas’s informational content is yet to be achieved, under the coordination of the OP-DCC steering group, a preliminary overview has been provided for the last EuroGOOS General Assembly (May ‘25). Besides the general corpus characteristics given above, some key features of the actual European OOFs community emerge:

- There is a striking inhomogeneity in the representation of OOFs dedicated to the different thematics. For instance, only a tiny fraction of reported systems are dedicated to biogeochemical or sea ice products (Fig. 2). The point was raised and discussed at EuroGOOS general assembly, and the consensus was this is not due to lack of interest for related operational products, but rather related to the complexity of the establishing such operational systems. Noteworthy, the relative representation of biogeochemistry OOFs in the DCC Atlas is actually less than it was in the EuroGOOS CWG survey (Sect. 3.1). We attribute this to the fact that the DCC Atlas census was more stringent on the technical readiness levels of modelling systems to include them as “operational systems”. This observation highlights that biogeochemical systems are ready and used for specific or research purposes, but that technical burden restrains their upgrading towards producing and disseminating OOFs.

Figure 2: Thematic distribution of European OOFs reported in the OP-DCC Atlas.

- It is a misconceived perception to see coastal OOFs as individually positioned between centralized regional OOFs (e.g. Copernicus Marine Service production centers) and local product and service delivery. It appears instead that the OOFs community is a tightly interlinked network, as most OOFs (56%) are both receivers and providers of open boundary conditions. Adhering to this perception leads to the conclusion that the establishment of a strong marine forecasting capacity around Europe does not only rely on enhancing regional products and supporting their uptake by local systems, but rather on promoting standards and practices to be adopted by both regional and local systems.
- OOFs data-dependency extends beyond ocean open boundary conditions. Atmospheric, land and tidal forcings are equally crucial in their production chain. This calls for coordinated efforts with e.g. other Copernicus services. A key element of information contained in the OP-DCC Atlas database is the detailed listings of upstream data providers, such as national meteorological or hydrological institutes (not listed here).

Figure 3: Upstream data dependency of European OOFs reported in the OP-DCC Atlas.

- In terms of downstream applications, a wide majority of the 127 European OOFs registered in the DCC-OP Atlas consider “Coastal Hazards” as a primary use of their systems (Fig. 4). Interestingly, “Research” comes next, and thus precedes any other operational applications. The most common operational applications are then “Search and rescue”, “Oil spill” and “Navigation support”, while the least represented applications include “Plastic Drift”, “Defense”, “Coupled weather forecasting” and “Iceberg drift”. Note that the information on “application” has here been collected by asking “Select the primary uses of the system (one or several)”, and does not proceed from a formal inspection of registered users or established downstream data flow.

Figure 4: Downstream applications of European OOFs reported in the OP-DCC Atlas.

4. The FOCCUS survey

4.1. Integration and extension of past inventories

The previous inventory and documentation exercises span a wide range of approaches and specificities (Sect. 3), each with assets and drawbacks as concerns the objectives of the present deliverable. The **CWG EuroGOOS inventory** reached a substantial corpus, through an extended data collection period and by remaining open to “quasi-operational” forecasting systems. Conclusions drawn might be slightly outdated (7 years), and do not target Copernicus Marine Service products explicitly. The **FOCCUS WP6 inventory** is strongly detailed from a technical point of view, but is limited to a corpus of 6 OOFS, all members of the FOCCUS consortium. The **Member State Marine Forum** is the richest in terms of enlightening institutional engagements, for instance w.r.t to European directives, and proceeds from a nominated representative board. However, the “channeling” of contributions through national representatives restricts the granularity of subsequent analysis (i.e. contributions and recommendations are not collected in a system-specific way). Finally, the **OP-DCC Atlas** is certainly the most constitutive contribution, being subscribed in the wider, long-term scope. The data collected consists more in detailed description of the forecasting systems and dependencies than in the collection of requirements of user needs. Also, and importantly, the OP-DCC Atlas analysis has only become available after the launch of the FOCCUS survey, hence preventing its consideration in the design of this new survey.

A number of converging conclusions emerge from these previous exercises, as well zones of shadow deserving attention in the new FOCCUS survey.

- First of all, there is wide disparity in the technical readiness level of OOFS operating in the different thematics covered by Copernicus Marine Service regional products: Hydrodynamics (PHY), Waves (WAV), biogeochemistry (BGC) and sea ice (ICE). Therefore, each of these thematics has its own bottlenecks, and strategic roadmaps should be drawn accordingly. Surveys with corpus restrained to strictly operational systems inevitably overlook the contributions from systems that are technically restrained in achieving an operational TRL status.
- Institutional integration, common practices, standards and protocols, adopted not only for Copernicus Marine Service production, but also promoted for downstream intermediate OOFS is strongly required to establish a dense inter-operable OOFS network. In this regard, OP-DCC clearly plays a leading role with the establishment of a systematic analysis of the architecture of the OOFS network and specific technical readiness milestones (Alvarez Fanjul et al., 2024).
- Handling data dependencies from a wide variety of sources remains a significant struggle for OOFS operators. Observation delivery time and technical alignment of model products constitutes important bottlenecks. Yet, the technical requirements are complex to apprehend, thematic-specific, and likely also system-specific as, in any given thematic, there is an important diversity of conceptual paradigms behind the modeling tools. The burden of specific pre-processing procedures therefore seems unavoidable. This means that Copernicus Marine Service products should not be thought of as final products perfectly fit for each system, but rather be proposed as comprehensive enough to be fine-tuned for specific needs, and come together with user support and centralized capacity building.

- There is an undeniably strong usage of Copernicus Marine Service products, and willingness to engage into strengthening this usage. Obviously, this means there are strong expectations in terms of product development.

4.2. Survey design and dissemination

Target information

Based on the above observations, a survey was designed targeting in particular to document the usage of Copernicus Marine Service model and observations products by local OOFs, and to identify user requirements for their improvement. The survey should allow declining the answer per thematic, and be contributed to by specific OOFs operators rather than overarching representatives. Aiming for an ideal balance between the time requested to contributors and the comprehensiveness of collected data, we limited contextual questions (e.g. administrative nature of the providing institutions, downstream services provided, etc ...) and leveraged synergy with the OP-DCC Atlas initiative by encouraging contributors to report their system in the Atlas, and refer to it in our survey. Finally, in order to personalize contributions to the survey, and make individual contributions as light as possible, a conditional design was adopted in which questions asked depend on previous answers. An extensive printout of the complete survey is provided as Annex to this deliverable (Sect. 8a).

Target audience and dissemination

The survey was designed in collaboration between RBINS, EuroGOOS, and MOI. This includes both the writing of questions, organisation of the conditional steps in the survey, and its implementation using the Typeform survey tools.

Dissemination

To ensure wide and relevant participation, the survey was disseminated through targeted outreach to known coastal and regional ocean observing and forecasting system (OOFs) operators via the EuroGOOS community network, as well as via direct contact lists curated by the FOCCUS partners. Communication was tailored to highlight the relevance of the survey to operators' day-to-day activities and planning, and to clarify how their inputs will directly contribute to improving the integration of Copernicus Marine data. The survey was also promoted via newsletter, multiple social media posts, email campaigns to partners and other relevant stakeholders (e.g. reference contacts listed in the DCC Atlas) and during relevant workshops and meetings, including those organised under FOCCUS and partner initiatives. This multi-channel approach aimed to maximise engagement while ensuring the quality and specificity of the responses.

GDPR

Ethics and GDPR are covered by the FOCCUS milestone MS1.1: GDPR-compliant project management portal created, including risk register. Part of this milestone included establishing an ethics statement with the EU Project Officer before the start of the project, and receiving agreement from the Consortium. See details of this milestone in Annex B.

5. Results

5.1 Corpus

Figure 5 : Map and product categories of the OOFs reported both in the FOCCUS survey and in the OP-DCC Atlas.

A total of 27 institutions contributed to the survey, reporting 34 European OOFs actively used to deliver hydrodynamics, wave, biogeochemistry and sea ice products. Among those, 20 systems were registered in the DCC Atlas (or have been registered for the purpose of the survey), which provides access to the extension of the corresponding domains. Together, these 20 domains cover a good part of the European coastline (Fig. 5), and range from city to regional spatial scale.

Figure 6 : (Left) Number of OOFs per product category. (Right) Intersection counts among these categories. Appartenance to a category is defined by the delivery of related products.

Most OOFs deliver products pertaining to more than one theme. For instance, 16 of the 19 OOFs delivering wave products also deliver hydrodynamic products, and 4 of those further extend to biogeochemical products (Fig 6). In terms of downstream application, the OOFs sampled in the FOCCUS survey (Fig. 7) reflects the tendency described for the larger corpus of the DCC-OP Atlas (Fig. 4), with “Coastal hazards” and “Research” as two main items, and “Defense” and “Plastic drift” in the least provided for thematics.

Figure 7 : Downstream applications of European OOFs reported in the FOCCUS survey.

5.2 Usage of Copernicus Marine Service products and recommendations

Physics - Model products

The hydrodynamic model products provided by Copernicus Marine Service are used as boundary or initial conditions in about 80% of the reported OOFs (Fig. 8). However, their usage requires some level of pre-processing for most OOFs (80%). Spatial downscaling is the most common procedure, while systematic bias correction is only considered in a few occasions for dynamical variables (current and elevation). Besides, other pre-processing procedures that were not among the survey propositions are often reported (~ 40%).

Figure 8: (Left) Usage of Copernicus Marine Service PHY products per different categories of OOFs. (Right) Pre-processing procedures.

Non-Copernicus Marine Service products are used for various variables, such as river flows, wave boundary conditions, but also for Copernicus Marine Service-distributed variables such as sea surface height and velocity (from remote sensing products), temperature and salinity. Scattered answers were given regarding the origin of alternative data sets, referring to large scale climatologies (e.g. World Ocean Atlas), or in-house large scale modelling system.

When asked if switching towards Copernicus Marine Service products within three years was an option, users of non-Copernicus Marine Service products responded as :

- “Yes, we’re working on it” (7)
- “No, because of current technical limitations with those products” (3)
- “No, it will take more than 3 years” (2)

Reasons for not using Copernicus Marine Service products in this case were only provided in two cases :

- “I do not know the river models in Copernicus database”
- “Internal rules”

Finally, when asked about clear improvement requests, the following answer were received :

- “Provide an re-forecast product before releasing forecasting product updates”
- “3D hourly fields available for the last 5 years”
- “More spatial distribution”
- “Improved spatial resolution”
- “[Date and time]: should be provided in current date / time”
- “The system includes the main river discharges of the study area.”
- “Copernicus Marine Service could integrate ML-based regression to fill gaps in HF radar and satellite-derived velocity or temperature data. Copernicus Marine Service also provides ensemble-based products. Additionally, vertical velocities should be included in numerical models.”

The survey then aimed at assessing the level of efforts required to use such products as boundary forcing conditions, and in particular whether there were some common

approaches that would justify preparing support material for their implementation. Only 10% of respondents find it relevant for Copernicus Marine Service to provide guidelines or support for the implementation of such methods.

Figure 9: Numerical scheme deployed to integrate Copernicus Marine Service products as boundary conditions.

Physics - Observations products

31 of the 34 reported OoFS make an active usage of Copernicus Marine Service PHY observation products, for validation or assimilation purposes. The most widely used observation platforms are fixed observatories, such as moorings and tide gauges, which are considered for all variables (temperature, salinity, currents and surface elevation), for validation as well as assimilation purposes. Remote sensing is more largely for temperature and sea surface height, which is logical given the maturity of those products, but cases are also reported that uses remote sensing salinity and surface currents products. Argo are popular for temperature and salinity. Finally, cruise and ship-cast datasets are the less commonly used data origins. Only two systems assimilate current velocity data, whereas about 8 systems report using temperature data for assimilation purposes.

Figure 10 : Reported use of Copernicus Marine Service PHY observation products for Oofs validation or assimilation purposes, classified per platform type and variable exploited.

Recommendations for improvements were collected in specific relation to validation or assimilation purposes. For validation purposes, the main claims were for :

- Increase data availability in the coastal / transitional areas (6), in particular users report tidal gauges, oceanographic buoys, and HF radar missing in the Copernicus Marine Service products.
- Improved quality flagging (3), in particular for NRT data, and making use of ML-based automation.
- Improved delivery delays (2).
- Wider spatial coverage.
- Increased spatial resolution.
- Dataset homogenization with standard NetCDF and spatial/temporal scales.
- Gap-filling in observational datasets using ML-based field reconstruction.
- Strengthened user support, via a GitHub repository, Jupyter Notebooks, and training workshops.

For assimilation purposes, the main claims were for :

- Increasing the availability of products in transitional areas (2)
- Enhance quality control (2)
- Faster data delivery in near-real time (2)
- More spatial and temporal distribution

Waves - Model products

11 of the 19 Waves Oofs rely, at least partly (7 only, 4 not only), on Copernicus Marine Service WAV model products for initial or boundary conditions . Widely used variables are the significant wave height, mean period and sea surface wave from direction. On the other hand, sea surface wind or swell wave characteristics, and Stokes drift velocities are less exploited. There is an equal proportion between usage “As Is”, after retrieval of spectral properties, or with another type of pre-processing.

Figure 11 : Usage and pre-processing protocols adopted for the use of Copernicus Marine Service WAV model products.

A wide majority of WAV model product improvements requests call for the provision of spectral information (8), with details pointing out:

- “Full directional spectra (e.g. hourly frequency for a reduced number of points)”.
- “2D spectral at some points”.
- “This is needed as boundary forcing for wave downscaling”.
- “Currently we rebuild the spectra using some approximations, which is not ideal”.

Other requests call for enhanced wave model accuracy for extreme storm peaks, and increase in the spatial resolution.

Waves OOFs not relying only on Copernicus Marine Service products are mainly obtaining the required information from in-house large scale models. Such users consider, in majority, switching to Copernicus Marine Service products within the next 3 years (70%), while some would not consider three years a sufficient time to implement such usage (10%) or are refrained by technical limitations (20%). Such limitations include the lack of wave spectral information (as highlighted by all those mentioning a technical limitation) and of very high resolution products.

Waves - Observation products

A majority of respondents use Copernicus Marine Service WAV observation products (79%), either for validation only (58%) , or validation and assimilation (21%). Request for improvements target specifically,

- for validation purposes :
 - (5) to increase the spatial coverage, and embed currently unconsidered wave buoys systems, with a special emphasis on coastal regions.
 - (2) to provide observed wave spectral information
 - More transparent quality control,

- Provision of technical information about the buoys
- for assimilation purposes:
 - Reduce delay from real time
 - Better quality control of spectral satellite wave products

Biogeochemistry - model products

The limited number (5) of BGC OOFS contributors to the survey limits the depth of this section’s analyses. However, all are users of Copernicus Marine Service BGC model products for initial or boundary conditions.

Figure 12 : Usage and pre-processing protocols adopted for the use of Copernicus Marine Service BIO model products.

Most commonly used products are oxygen and nutrients, while POM, pH, Zooplankton and beam attenuation are seldomly used. We note that products are never used “as is”, but always involve some level of pre-processing, without clear trends about the suggested options. Recommended improvements includes :

- (3) “Increasing the temporal resolution of the available products”
- “We have to work on the difference between using Chla or Phytoplankton”

Variables found from other sources include dissolved and particulate nitrogen and phosphorus. 2 respondents do consider Copernicus Marine Service products within the next 3 years, whereas one remains limited by technical limitations in this regard.

Biogeochemistry - observation products

All BGC OOFS rely on some Copernicus Marine Service BIO observational datasets. The number of contributions received is too restricted to draw generalities, but we can note that no use of ship-cast data is reported, and that, besides chlorophyll, there are no systematic

considerations among the biogeochemical variables for validation or assimilation purposes (Fig. 13). The major recommendations for biogeochemical observation products are calls to expand data coverage in the coastal and transitional areas, and a mention concerning the restricted number of Bio-Argo floats.

Figure 13 : Reported use of Copernicus Marine Service BIO observation products for OOFs validation or assimilation purposes, classified per platform type and variable exploited.

Sea ice

There are 3 ICE OOFs reported in the survey, and two of them rely on Copernicus Marine Service ICE model products. Both use sea ice concentration and sea ice thickness, but only one uses sea ice velocity. A recommendation is made to provide ice thickness in terms of sea ice classes.

In terms of observations, 2 systems use Copernicus Marine Service ICE observation products for validation, and one of them also for assimilation. The call for a provision sea ice thickness data per class is repeated in the case of observation products, while noting that definitions might differ between SI TAC and regional models. Sea ice observation products near the coast are also missing.

Figure 14 : Usage of Copernicus Marine Service ICE model products.

6. Conclusions

There is an undeniably strong usage of Copernicus Marine Service products, and a user willingness to engage into strengthening this usage. Among users of non-Copernicus Marine Service products, we note similar proportions in the intentions to engage in Copernicus Marine Service model products for the WAV and PHY OOFs: about 70% are ready to switch to Copernicus Marine Service products within the next 3 years, 20% think there remains some product quality restriction to do so, and 10% considers that is technically too demanding to do so within the next 3 years. This means there are strong expectations in terms of product development, but also confidence in the capacity of Copernicus Marine Service to proceed with these developments.

All surveys and inventory exercises point towards a large disparity in the representation of OOFs active in the different thematics. The proportion of biogeochemical systems is about 18% in the EuroGOOS CWG inventory, 6% in the DCC Atlas, and 14% in the FOCCUS survey. Noteworthy, the relative representation of biogeochemistry OOFs in the DCC Atlas is actually less than it was in the EuroGOOS CWG survey, which was achieved 5 years earlier. We attribute this to the fact that the DCC Atlas census was more stringent on the technical readiness levels of modelling systems to include them as “operational systems”. This highlights that biogeochemical systems do exist, and are ready and used for specific or research purposes, but that some factors restrain their “upgrade” towards producing and disseminating OOFs. It would seem relevant to dig in the reasons for these limitations, i.e. distinguishing bottlenecks issued from the availability and quality of data dependencies, from the technical burden of handling the dependency datasets, or from the effort required to establish the last operationalization step (e.g.: the need for stable institutional resources

and/or the technical burden of setting up routine execution and dissemination protocols). Indeed, there are specific actionable means that could help unlock bottlenecks of these different nature. In general terms, the OP-DCC Atlas is an important component that could help Copernicus Marine Service in targeting its user-support service. One could imagine, for instance, that a user requesting Copernicus Marine Service support is given the possibility (or asked) to reference its DCC-Atlas entry, hence providing the contextual information allowing to tailor the provided support (be it provided by humans or AI agents). However, if the aim is to “activate” quasi-operational systems, the scope of the OP-DCC Atlas should then be enlarged to such candidate OOFs, while relying on operational readiness levels to sort them out.

The OP-DCC Atlas and FOCCUS surveys help in highlighting the interconnected nature of the OOFs community. 66% of European OOFs are both receivers and providers of boundary conditions from or towards other OOFs. Also, most OOFs are not restricted to one single thematic, but deliver products related to several. To enforce the European OOFs capacity, it thus appears that i) the effort required to enforce interoperability and smooth out data linkage should not be restricted to centralized regional units (Copernicus Marine Service), but rather enforced for all systems, ii) any enhancement is likely to have cascading effects, along chains of spatially nested OOFs and chains of coupled systems embedding several thematics.

It appears that using forcing products and implementing suitable boundary condition schemes remains an important technical challenge for most users. While some procedures are common (e.g., bias correction and spatial downscaling, variable remapping for sea-ice and biogeochemical systems, spectral information recovery for waves), the majority of users mentions “other pre-processing protocols”, not listed in our pre-formulated propositions. Likely, this relates to the wide diversity of modelling tools and their conceptual formulations of marine dynamics. In this context, it seems irrelevant to aim for single “perfect” products matching the needs of every user. Instead, Copernicus Marine Service products should be comprehensive enough to contain the required data and specifications allowing every user to adapt it for its own need. This is particularly true for “complex thematics” (se-ice, biogeochemistry), where the difference in conceptual approaches is more pronounced (e.g. fixed or free stoichiometric characterization of various components, level of details and classification of phytoplankton groups or sea-ice categories). Obviously, such comprehensive products can come along with facilitation of local adaptation procedures, in terms of data standards, capacity building and user support. On this last regard, some contributions in some surveys support the idea of benefitting from centralized resources (e.g. workshops, git repos with notebooks, etc...), but there is no strong consensus on this point.

Finally, the main recommendations trends for specific products are given per thematic below:

- Physics
 - Model: delivery of re-forecast products, of 3D hourly fields over large periods, and ensemble-based products.
 - Obs.: Enhanced and potentially ML-based quality control, improved NRT delivery delays, enhanced coverage of coastal and transitional areas. In

particular users report tidal gauges, oceanographic buoys, and HF radar missing in the Copernicus Marine Service products.

- Waves
 - There is a strong call for the delivery of spectral information, both for model and observation products.
 - Obs. : Enhanced quality and transparency in the quality control procedure, and product documentation (e.g. technical characteristics of wave buoys).
- Biogeochemistry
 - Model : Embrace the specificities of biogeochemical systems complexity. For instance, chlorophyll is not a straightforward proxy for phytoplankton biomass but ambiguous shortcomings in the interoperability between model, in-situ and remote sensing products remains.
 - Obs. : Expand coverage in coastal and transitional waters; Support the deployment of additional Bio-Argo floats.
- Sea-ice :
 - Model: A clear recommendation is made to provide ice thickness in terms of classes.
 - Obs.: The call for a provision sea ice thickness data per class is repeated, while noting that definitions might differ between SI TAC and regional models. Sea ice observation products near the coast are also missing.

8. Annexes

Annex A : The FOCCUS Survey on Copernicus Marine Service dependencies, as published through Typeforms and distributed on 1st Jan 2025

DISCLAIMER : This is an exhaustive transcript of the questions asked in the survey. However, the survey is interactive and responsive, in the sense that the questions asked and the order in which they are asked is dependent on the answer given to previous questions. The survey experienced by contributors should therefore be shorter than the exhaustive transcript reproduced hereunder.

<https://marinecopernicus.typeform.com/to/Bew6WtKe>

FOCCUS Survey

Copernicus products in coastal forecasting centers

The Horizon Europe FOCCUS project aims for a coastal extension of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service.

This survey aims to document the current use of Copernicus products by coastal forecasting centers, and is thus addressed to the developers and maintainers of such forecasting systems. Thanks to your contributions, we aim to guide the roadmap towards a future enhanced integration of the open ocean and coastal operational oceanography systems.

For efficiency, we will complement your contribution by collecting information on your forecasting system from the Ocean Decade OceanPrediction Atlas. Although not mandatory, please consider registering to this Atlas before addressing the present survey.

This survey addresses different topics : physical oceanography, biogeochemistry, waves and sea ice. Feel free to send this survey to anyone in your organisation who may be able to answer one or more parts of it.

For any inquiries, please contact acapet@naturalsciences.be.

Q1a : Is your OOFS* reported in the OceanPrediction DCC Atlas? (*Ocean Operational forecasting System)

- Yes
- No

Q1b*[if Q1a==Yes]* : Please indicate the corresponding reference: Please copy the exact name used for your system in the DCC Atlas entry

Q2a*[if Q1a==No]* : Registering your OOFS in the DCC Atlas enables us to directly utilize the information stored there to better contextualize your responses to this survey. Therefore, we strongly encourage you to register.

If you are not yet registered, we will require some additional information from you.

Q2b*[if Q1a==No]* : What is the name of your organization/institution ?

Q2c*[if Q1a==No]* : Where are you based? [-> *list of European countries*]

Q2d*[if Q1a==No]* : What is (are) your regional basin(s) of interest ?[-> *list of European marine basins* ?]

Q2e*[if Q1a==No]* : At what scale do you work ? [-> *List of spatial scales*]

Q3a : Do your Oofs produces/provides products related to physical oceanography (excluding waves)?

- Yes
- No [-> *skips all the following Q3 questions.*]

Q3b *[only if Q3a==YES]* :Do your Oofs* relies on operational Copernicus Marine Service **physical oceanography model data** products for initial and/or open boundary conditions?

- Yes, we only use Copernicus Marine Service products.
- Yes, but not only.
- No.

Q3c *[only if Q3b==Yes (only or not only)]* : What specific variable(s) from model data do you use, and do you need to apply any specific processing to those products before their consideration in your operational pipeline? [-> *Matrix of checkboxes*]

	I don't use it	I use it and apply a spatial downscaling procedure	I use it and adapt the temporal variability	I use it and apply systematic bias correction	I use it, with another type of pre-processing	I use it as it is
Temperature	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salinity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Velocity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sea surface height	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q3d: Can you identify potential improvements of physical oceanography products that would enhance the interface between the Copernicus Marine Service system and your

Oofs? *If relevant, please start by indicating the related variable, eg. "[Temperature] : should be provided in Fahrenheit"*

Q3e [*only if Q3b==Not only*] : For what variable(s) are you relying on another data provider for initial and open boundary conditions?

Q3f [*only if Q3b==No*] Which data provider are you relying on for initial and open boundary conditions?

- World Ocean Atlas or other climatology products.
- Large-scale ocean models maintained in our own institution
- Large scale ocean models provided by external institutions other than Copernicus Marine Service (-> *this opens a free text option: What other institution?*)
- We don't need such inputs.
- Other

Q3g [*only if Q3b==No, or not only*] : Would using Copernicus Marine Service products be an option within the next 3 years?

- Yes, we're working on it.
- No, it would require more than 3 years to be implemented.
- No, because of current technical limitations with those products (-> *this opens a free text option: What limitation?*)
- No because of other reasons (-> *this opens a free text option: What reasons?*).

Q3h [*only if Q3g==No because of "other reasons" or "technical limitations".*] : For what reasons or limitations ?

Q3i : What type of scheme/methods are you using for boundary conditions? [*Multiple selections allowed*]

- Radiation/Orlanski or similar conditions to allow outgoing wave propagation and avoid artificial reflection of outgoing waves into the domain.
- Flather or similar conditions to ensure a balance between sea level and current interactions, and enhance dynamic consistency.
- Flow Relaxation or similar scheme to reduce discontinuity and ensure smooth transitions at boundaries.
- None of the above.
- Other (-> *this opens a free text option*)

Q3j [*only if Q3i != "None of the above"*] : Would you consider it relevant/helpful if common guidelines for the application of such methods would be provided/supported in the frame of Copernicus Marine Services.

Q3k : Do your Oofs rely on Copernicus Marine Service **observation** products for **validation**?

- Yes
- No

Q3l: [only if Q3k==Yes] From which platform?

	Remote Sensing	Argo and other moving autonomous platform	Moorings, tide gauges, and other fixed platforms	Cruises, and ship-cast datasets
Temperature	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salinity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Velocity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sea surface height	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q3m : Can you identify an improvement in the **observation** product that would help improve its usage in the **validation** procedure?

Q3n : Do your OOFs rely on Copernicus Marine Service **observation** products for **assimilation**?

- Yes
- No

Q3o [only if Q3n==Yes] : From which platform?

	Remote Sensing	Argo and other moving autonomous platform	Moorings, tide gauges, and other fixed platforms	Cruises, and ship-cast datasets
Temperature	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salinity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Velocity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sea surface height	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q3p: Can you identify an improvement in the observation product that would help improve its usage in the assimilation procedure?

Q4a. Do your OOFs produces/provides products related to biogeochemical oceanography?

- Yes
- No [-> Skips all following Q4 questions]

Q4b [only if Q4a==YES] Do your OOFs relies on operational Copernicus Marine Service biogeochemical oceanography **model** data products for initial and/or open boundary conditions?

- Yes, we only use Copernicus Marine Service products.
- Yes, but not only.
- No.

Q4c [only if Q4b==YES (only or not only)] What specific product(s)?

	I don't use it	I use it and implement a specific remapping of state variables	I use it and adapt the temporal variability	I use it and apply systematic bias correction	I use it, with another type of pre-processing	I use it as it is
Chlorophyll-A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Light attenuation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Zooplankton	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nutrients	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Oxygen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
pH	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Particulate Organic Matter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q4d Can you identify potential improvements of biogeochemical oceanography products that would enhance the interface between the Copernicus Marine Service system and your Oofs?

Q4e [only if Q4b==Not only] : For what variable(s) are you relying on another data provider for initial and open boundary conditions?

Q4f [only if Q4b==No, or not only] Which data provider are you relying on for initial and open boundary conditions?

- World Ocean Atlas or other climatology products.
- Large-scale BGC models maintained in our own institution
- Large scale BGC models provided by external institutions other than Copernicus Marine Service.
- We don't need such inputs.

Q4g [only if Q4b==No, or not only] Would using Copernicus Marine Service products be an option within the next 3 years?

- Yes, we're working on it.
- No, it would require more than 3 years to be implemented.
- No, because of current technical limitations with those products.
- No, because of other reasons.

Q4h [only if Q4g==No because of "other reasons" or "technical limitations".] :
For what reasons or limitations ?

Q4i For **validation** of your biogeochemical products, do your Oofs rely on Copernicus Marine Service observation products ?

- Yes
- No

Q4j [only if Q4i==Yes] From which platform?

	Remote Sensing	Argo and other moving autonomous platform	Moorings, tide gauges, and other fixed platforms	Cruises, and ship-cast datasets
Chlorophyll-A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Light attenuation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Zooplankton	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Oxygen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nutrients	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
pH	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Particulate Organic Matter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q4i Can you identify an improvement in the observation product that would help improve its usage in the **validation** procedure?

Q4j For **assimilation** of your biogeochemical products, do your OOFs rely on Copernicus Marine Service observation products ?

- Yes
- No

Q4h [only if Q4j==Yes] From which platform?

	Remote Sensing	Argo and other moving autonomous platform	Moorings, tide gauges, and other fixed platforms	Cruises, and ship-cast datasets
Chlorophyll-A	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Light attenuation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Turbidity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Zooplankton	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nutrients	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Oxygen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
pH	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q4i Can you identify an improvement in the observation product that would help improve its usage in the **assimilation** procedure?

Q5a. Do your OOFs produces/provides products related to waves?

- Yes
- No [-> Skips all following Q5 questions]

Q5b Do your OOFs relies on operational Copernicus Marine Service wave model data products for initial and/or open boundary conditions?

- Yes, we only use Copernicus Marine Service products.
- Yes, but not only.
- No.

Q5c [only if Q3.1==YES (only or not only)] What specific product(s)?

	I don't use it	retrieve spectral properties from the products	I use it and adapt the temporal variability	I use it and apply systematic bias correction	with another type of pre-processing	I use it as it is
Sea surface wave stokes drift velocity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
wave significant height (SWH)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
wave mean period (MWT)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sea surface wave from direction (VMDR)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sea surface wind wave significant height or period (WW)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sea surface swell wave height or period (SW1)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q5d Can you identify potential improvements of wave products that would enhance the interface between the Copernicus Marine Service system and your OOFs?

Q5e [only if Q5b==Not only] : For what variable(s) are you relying on another data provider for initial and open boundary conditions?

Q5f [only if Q5b==No, or not only] Which data provider are you relying on for initial and open boundary conditions?

- World Ocean Atlas or other climatology products.
- Large-scale wave models maintained in our own institution
- Large scale wave models provided by external institutions other than Copernicus Marine Service.
- We don't need such inputs.

Q5g [only if Q5b==No, or not only] Would using Copernicus Marine Service products be an option within the next 3 years?

- Yes, we're working on it.
- No, it would require more than 3 years to be implemented.
- No, because of current technical limitations with those products
- No because of other reasons

Q5h [only if Q5g==No because of "other reasons" or "technical limitations".] :
For what reasons or limitations ?

Q5i For **validation** of your wave products, do your OOFS rely on Copernicus Marine Service observation products ?

- Yes
- No

Q5j Can you identify an improvement in the observation product that would help improve its usage in the **validation** procedure?

Q5k For **assimilation** of your wave products, do your OOFS rely on Copernicus Marine Service observation products ?

- Yes
- No

Q5i Can you identify an improvement in the observation product that would help improve its usage in the **assimilation** procedure?

Q6a. Do your OOFS produces/provides products related to sea-ice?

- Yes
- No [-> Skips all following Q6 questions]

Q6b Do your OOFS relies on operational Copernicus Marine Service sea ic model data products for initial and/or open boundary conditions?

- Yes, we only use Copernicus Marine Service products.
- Yes, but not only.
- No.

Q6c [only if Q6b==Yes (only or not only)] What specific variable(s) from model data do you use, and do you need to apply any specific processing to those products before their consideration in your operational pipeline?

	I don't use it	I use it and implement a specific remapping of state variables	I use it and adapt the temporal variability	I use it and apply systematic bias correction	I use it, with another type of pre-processing	I use it as it is
Sea ice velocity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Snow	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Albedo	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Iceberg	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sea ice thickness	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
sea ice concentration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q6d Can you identify potential improvements of sea ice products that would enhance the interface between the Copernicus Marine Service system and your OOFs?

Q6e [only if Q6b==Not only] : For what variable(s) are you relying on another data provider for initial and open boundary conditions?

Q6f [only if Q6b==No, or not only] Which data provider are you relying on for initial and open boundary conditions?

- World Ocean Atlas or other climatology products.
- Large-scale models maintained in our own institution
- Large scale models provided by external institutions other than Copernicus Marine Service.
- We don't need such inputs.

Q6g [only if Q6b==No, or not only] Would using Copernicus Marine Service products be an option within the next 3 years?

- Yes, we're working on it.

- No, it would require more than 3 years to be implemented.
- No, because of current technical limitations with those products
- No because of other reasons

Q6h [only if Q6g==No because of “other reasons” or “technical limitations”.] :
For what reasons or limitations ?

Q6i For **validation** of your sea ice products, do your OOFS rely on Copernicus Marine Service observation products ?

- Yes
- No

Q6j Can you identify an improvement in the observation product that would help improve its usage in the **validation** procedure?

Q6k For **assimilation** of your sea ice products, do your OOFS rely on Copernicus Marine Service observation products ?

- Yes
- No

Q6l Can you identify an improvement in the observation product that would help improve its usage in the **assimilation** procedure?

Q7 If you would allow us to contact you for questions on your contributions, please fill your email below

Annex B: Referenced Items

Description of the coastal systems implemented downstream of Copernicus Marine Service through the Monitoring and Forecast Centres (MFC), responsible partners and interfaces with Copernicus Marine Service:

Coastal System(s)	Copernicus service	Partner(s)	FOCCUS activities(all interface with CMEMS)
1) "Norkyst"	ARC MFC BAL MFC	MET.NO, NERSC	Multi-platform data assimilation; DA observation impacts; land-ocean coupling. PHYS.
2) "NEMO-IM"	BAL MFC	SMHI	Nesting to very high resolution (~50 m); land-ocean coupling. PHYS.
3) "GCOAST-GB" 4) "GCOAST-BS"	NWS MFC BS MFC	HEREON MHD	Land-ocean coupling, AI-for probabilistic forecasting. PHYS and BGC.
5) "DKSS"	NWS MFC	DMI	Multi-model ensemble forecasting. PHYS.
6) "DCSM-FM"	NWS MFC	DELTARES	Land-ocean coupling. PHYS and BGC.
7) "COHERENS"	NWS	RBINS	EPS forcing. PHYS and BGC.
8) "Tolosa-SW"/ 9) "CROCO"	GLO MFC IBI MFC	SHOM MOi	EPS and uncertainty estimation; ML assisted post processing for forecasting. PHYS.
10)"ADRIFS" 11) "Lazio coast"	MED MFC	CMCC	AI-assisted DA; EPS and uncertainty estimation. PHYS and BGC.
12) "Shyfer-CNR"	MED MFC	CNR	AI-assisted DA; PHYS.
13) WMOP	MED MFC	SOCIB	Multi-platform DA. PHYS.
14) LisOcean	MED MFC	+ATLANTIC	Multi-platform DA. PHYS.

Table 1.2b: Description of the coastal systems implemented downstream of CMEMS through the Monitoring and Forecast Centres (MFC), responsible partners and interfaces with CMEMS.

Milestone MS1.1 summary:

MS1.1 GDPR compliant project management portal created, including risk register is a milestone which was delivered, following the PO's request before the start of the FOCCUS Project. After communications to refine the ethics statement with the previous Project Officer in the project communication section of the EU Portal, an email with the agreed-upon statement was circulated to Consortium in March 2025, with the request to reply if there were any objections. Email content was as follows:

"Ethics response:

In the course of the organization of meetings, the names and email addresses of the participants will be collected. During recruitments, more detailed personal information (e.g., in the form of CVs) will be collected by the respective partners.

For all partners in the FOCCUS consortium, the following measures are in place to guarantee data protection:

- *Existence of information security and data protection regulations*
- *Obligation of the employees involved in data processing to maintain confidentiality (Art. 28 Para. 3 Sentence 1 Letter b GDPR, Art. 29 GDPR) as well as issuing information on data protection*
- *Data protection training for employees*
- *Instructing employees regarding IT use and information security, data protection and data backup*
- *Determination of responsibilities and responsibilities for devices and systems*
- *Exclusive use of authorized company-owned IT systems or external systems tested by information technology before use*

Regarding the use of AI: The team has not identified any ethical issues surrounding the use of AI in this project, including ethical issues related to human rights and values. The use of AI-based algorithms is for very restricted and clearly defined FOCCUS purposes, namely for improving the quality and to advance coastal observations and models. Therefore, there cannot be any potential discrimination against humans as a result of the system, and the system will not have any potential to lead to negative social or environmental impacts.”

This milestone was then recorded as completed in the EU Portal upon the receipt of zero objections.

Milestone MS6.1: Interface Roadmaps for Improved Interfacing with Copernicus Marine Service:

Roadmaps for improving each coastal system’s interfacing with Copernicus was created in M6 of the project. A summary of this milestone can be found below, as it is not available on the EU Portal or for public dissemination.

Additionally, the Commission has the right to request access to the documents that make up this milestone directly using the project’s shared drive here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1tImc7NZxheF69Is86elyiv3eLRsgggPH?usp=drive_link

These roadmaps include a summary of each member state coastal system, the Copernicus Marine model products used, as well as a description of the existing nesting method used. Crucially, these roadmaps detail for each coastal system the proposed improvements in this nesting, and will be used for the work outlined in the DoA in WP6/7.

6. References

- Alvarez Fanjul, E., Ciliberti, S., Pearlman, J., Wilmer-Becker, K., Bahurel, P., Arduin, F., Arnaud, A., Azizzadenesheli, K., Aznar, R., Bell, M., Bertino, L., Behera, S., Brassington, G., Calewaert, J. B., Capet, A., Chassignet, E., Ciavatta, S., Cirano, M., Clementi, E., ... Zufic, R. (2024). Promoting best practices in ocean forecasting through an Operational Readiness Level. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, *11*, 1443284.
- Capet, A., Fernández, V., She, J., Dabrowski, T., Umgiesser, G., Staneva, J., Mészáros, L., Campuzano, F., Ursella, L., Nolan, G., & El Serafy, G. (2020). Operational Modeling Capacity in European Seas—An EuroGOOS Perspective and Recommendations for Improvement. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, *7*, 129.